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Mechanisms for the Development of Event Tourism as a Key Component of Azerbaijan's Economy

KEYWORDS

event tourism,
Azerbaijan,
holding events,
development of
regions,
improvement
mechanisms,
international
experience

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of studying the current state of event tourism in Azerbaijan lies in its potential to stimulate economic growth, strengthen the country's international reputation, and preserve its cultural heritage.

The paper aims to identify and analyze opportunities for the development of event tourism in Azerbaijan.

Materials and methods. The study draws on statistical data regarding the number of tourists attending celebrations and festivals across various regions of Azerbaijan, as well as case studies of successful event projects. The research methods include document analysis and statistical evaluation to assess the scale and dynamics of event tourism.

Results. Numerous holidays and festivals are organized annually in different regions of Azerbaijan, significantly contributing to the development of event tourism. Successfully planned and well-organized, such events play a crucial role in driving economic growth, fostering cultural exchange, and enhancing the international visibility of Azerbaijan regions.

The current state of event tourism is examined with reference to major events held in the country. For example, in its first four years, the Formula 1 Grand Prix generated approximately \$500 million for the Azerbaijani economy. In April 2023, the Formula 1 Grand Prix of Azerbaijan attracted 154,233 visitors from more than 100 countries, many visiting the country for the first time.

Conclusion. To strengthen event tourism in Azerbaijan, a range of measures should be prioritized, including infrastructure expansion, investment and financing, strategic marketing, workforce training, and innovative practices. By combining best international practices with local cultural and regional characteristics, Azerbaijan can build a sustainable and competitive event tourism sector that contributes to long-term economic and social development.

FOR CITATION

Received: Dec 27, 2024
Accepted: Mar 12, 2025
Published: Jun 1, 2025

Akhundova, A. G. (2025). Mechanisms for the Development of Event Tourism as a Key Component of Azerbaijan's Economy. *Economic Consultant*, (2), 42–57. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2025.2.3>

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INTRODUCTION

Analyzing the current state of event tourism in Azerbaijan is crucial for stimulating economic growth, enhancing international recognition, and preserving cultural heritage. Developing event tourism attracts diverse audiences, expands the tourism offering, and creates new employment opportunities. Assessing the sector's current performance highlights challenges and identifies opportunities to improve event effectiveness, supporting strategic planning and sustainable tourism development in Azerbaijan.

Event tourism is a rapidly growing segment of the global tourism industry, expanding by approximately 1.5% annually. It plays a key role in boosting local economies, attracting investment, and promoting cultural exchange. In Azerbaijan, with its rich historical and cultural heritage, event tourism presents significant potential. However, regional development faces several obstacles that require targeted solutions to fully leverage these opportunities.

This study focuses on examining the current state of event tourism in Azerbaijan, evaluating its socio-economic potential for regional development, and proposing strategies for improvement.

Specifically, it investigates mechanisms to enhance event tourism, including identifying challenges, assessing potential, and recommending measures to strengthen infrastructure, financing, marketing, and other critical areas, while incorporating international best practices.

The Belt and Road Initiative, launched by China, aims to enhance infrastructure and strengthen connections among Eurasian countries. In Azerbaijan, this initiative offers new opportunities for tourism sector growth.

H. Thees and A. Schuhbert highlight that the Belt and Road Initiative improves connectivity and accessibility for destinations along the Ancient Silk Road, with the success of the route depending heavily on cross-border cooperation [1].

Wood et al. note that Central Asia's unique attractions provide diverse, high-quality experiences year-round, potentially driving sustainable economic growth. Key policies, including the Belt and Road Initiative, support infrastructure projects that improve integration with regional tourism markets [2].

K. Thirumaran et al. emphasize that the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), spanning from the Caspian Sea to China's western border and encompassing five major countries along the ancient Silk Road, has untapped tourism potential. While the historical route has long-standing significance, its modern development is in early stages, and regional countries aim both to attract international tourists and to capture a growing share of the global tourism market [3].

R. F. Sabacan et al. argue that the Belt and Road Initiative, through extensive onshore and offshore infrastructure projects, stimulates trade and tourism along the route. They recommend that participating countries strengthen trade relations to maximize tourism benefits [4].

Sustainable tourism development in Azerbaijan requires balancing economic growth with the preservation of cultural and natural heritage and environmental responsibility. This involves developing eco-friendly routes, protecting historical sites, supporting local communities, and integrating environmental standards into infrastructure planning.

L. Aliyeva and S. Rzayeva observe that tourism ranks among the most promising non-oil sectors in Azerbaijan. They identify factors and conditions that support sustainable tourism development, creating opportunities for growth and enhancing the country's competitiveness in international tourism rankings. Azerbaijan's territory features a long history, rich cultural monuments, favorable geographic location, attractive natural landscapes, and a diverse cultural and religious heritage.

According to researchers, key drivers of tourism development in Azerbaijan include support for private initiatives in product development, coordination at local and regional levels, responsiveness to consumer demand, and the strengthening of regional and thematic tourism offerings. Coordinating engaging and attractive tourism products is also essential. The combination of traditional and modern medical institutions with natural resources, such as naphthalenic oil and Salt Mountain in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, provides opportunities for developing health tourism [5].

A. Aliyev et al. note that eastern Azerbaijan hosts over 350 mud volcanoes on land and at sea, varying in type, morphology, size, and eruption activity. These unique geological formations attract both geologists and tourists. The authors highlight seven notable mud volcanoes, emphasizing their value not only as geological objects but also as landscape features and local attractions [6].

G. Giorgadze examines the development potential of the Mtkvari River, highlighting its historical, informational, and recreational significance. The study focuses on the river's geographical and climatic characteristics, historical importance, and the aesthetic and structural features of its channel and banks. Giorgadze emphasizes the need to explore new approaches for the spatial and functional expansion of the historic "Caravan Route" [7].

A. Umudov analyzes how Azerbaijan's political system influences environmental policy, reviewing the historical evolution of environmental management in the country, including the period prior to the collapse of the Soviet Union [8].

Despite its potential, tourism development in Azerbaijan faces several challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, limited international promotion, political and conflict-related risks, and the need to preserve cultural and natural heritage.

M. Hashimli provides a comprehensive review of government tourism strategies, noting that restrictive visa regimes, high air transport costs, and insufficient accommodation limit the sector's sustainable development. Addressing these issues is essential for fully realizing Azerbaijan's tourism potential [9].

R. Abbasov et al. argue that the Caspian Sea's tourist and recreational resources are used inefficiently, and poor management has prevented the sea from becoming a true tourism hub. Pollution and inadequate maintenance of coastal areas have rendered much of the shoreline unsuitable for beach use. A survey conducted among coastal residents revealed that, in recent decades, communities have largely disengaged from the Caspian, shifting to activities unrelated to the sea [10].

F. Mola et al. note that the Caspian Sea's coastal zones are in a critical state due to an imbalance between tourism development and environmental protection, leading to declining attractiveness. Their study, focused on the Iranian coastline, highlights the negative environmental impacts of tourism. The authors emphasize that raising public awareness of these consequences is a necessary first step toward sustainable development [11].

Y. Abasova and B. Ganiyeva-Dadashova examine the quality of higher education in tourism and hospitality, identifying gaps between university training and the practical demands of the tourism labor market in Azerbaijan [12].

S. Mohammadi and S. Rasekhi analyze the relationship between tourism and environmental performance in Caspian Sea countries from 2002 to 2013. Their findings show that international tourism responds positively to ecological indicators,

the Human Development Index, GDP per capita, and trade openness. By contrast, environmental indicators respond negatively to tourism shocks and GDP per capita. However, they react positively to improvements in human capital, trade openness, and GDP per capita. Based on these results, the authors recommend that Caspian states give greater attention to environmental issues in tourism development [13].

A. D. Abdullayev points out that health tourism in Azerbaijan has only recently become the subject of systematic study. Research in this area has focused on the legal framework, financial issues, and the role of the state in implementing national tourism policy. Abdullayev evaluates the current state of health tourism and identifies recent development trends [14].

N. Akhundova explores tourism's role in intersectoral development in Azerbaijan, analyzing national data to inform strategies for strengthening the sector. The study highlights the need for increased public funding, greater investment, and stronger promotion of Azerbaijani tourism products in both domestic and international markets [15].

Overall, the literature shows that Central Asia's unique attractions, combined with infrastructure development, provide favorable conditions for attracting tourists and fostering regional cooperation. The Eurasian Economic Union, situated along the historic Silk Road, has the potential to emerge as a dynamic tourism destination if member states fully develop domestic capacity and strengthen trade relations.

In terms of Azerbaijani economy, researchers consistently emphasize the importance of tourism, supported by its rich history, cultural heritage, favorable location, and natural resources. For sustainable growth, the industry requires support for private initiatives, coordination across multiple levels, responsiveness to consumer demand, and the development of regional and thematic segments, including health tourism.

Based on the above, it is important to analyze the potential of cultural, sports, and other large-scale events for the development of the country's tourism sector.

At the same time, several persistent challenges limit the sector's potential. These include restrictive visa policies, high airfares, insufficient accommodation, and the underutilization of Caspian Sea resources due to pollution and inadequate coastal management. The lack of balance between tourism expansion and environmental protection further undermines competitiveness, underscoring the need for stronger public awareness and sustainable development practices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study relied on two main sources of data: statistics on the number of tourists attending festive events and festivals in different regions of Azerbaijan, along with the income they generated; and case studies of successful event projects in the country.

Methods included the analysis of documents and statistical data to evaluate the scale and dynamics of event tourism.

To review the literature, articles published in several authoritative journals were examined, including *Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation*, *Geoheritage, Societies and Political Orders in Transition*, *Journal of Sustainable Development*, *Iranian Journal of Economic Studies*, *WSEAS Transactions on Environment and Development*, and *the Journal of International Relations and Development*.

RESULTS

Event tourism is one of the fastest-growing sectors of the global tourism industry, encompassing events of various scales and types—such as cultural festivals, sporting competitions, business conferences, and exhibitions. This form of tourism can make a significant contribution to regional economic development by improving infrastructure, creating employment opportunities, and fostering cultural exchange. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), events are currently regarded as a key driver of tourism growth in many parts of the world, with their share in the overall system of global tourism increasing by 1.5% annually.

Event tourism is an integral part of the broader tourism industry, characterized by travel to a destination at a particular time in connection with an event or with a significant occasion in the life of a community. Events themselves are designed to communicate specific messages or appeals to target audiences. To achieve this communication effect, public relations departments often organize press conferences, opening ceremonies, product launches, and similar activities.

As a commercial segment, event tourism is well established abroad, particularly in the United States, Italy, France, South Korea, and the United Kingdom. Today, dozens of cities have specialized economies centered on events. Many experts argue that Australia leads the field in event tourism development, owing to its clear system of strategic planning that maximizes tourism benefits for destinations.

For example, each January, Melbourne becomes a global focal point with the Grand Slam tennis tournament, the Australian Open, attracting hundreds of thousands of tourists eager to watch the world's top players. The Melbourne Cup, held annually since 1861 on the first Tuesday of November, has become more than a sporting event – it is now a cultural phenomenon that captures the attention of the entire country.

The Sydney-Hobart International Regatta, held every December 26 since 1945, continues to attract renowned sailors from across the world. Since 1985, Melbourne has also hosted the Formula 1 World Championship in March, with races held at the Albert Park street circuit, located near the city's business district and waterfront. This event consistently attracts more than 400,000 spectators, both residents and tourists. In 2023, the Australian Grand Prix set a new record with 444,631 attendees over the course of the weekend.

Australia also hosts many other high-profile events, including the annual Marathon of Mercy, international golf tournaments, Halloween celebrations, New Year's Eve festivities, and the Melbourne Wine and Food Festival. The latter, with its two-week world-class program, draws hundreds of thousands of culinary tourists each year. Collectively, these events enhance Australia's reputation as a highly attractive destination for international visitors.

Analysis of mega-events in Azerbaijan

A key priority for any modern state is the rapid and efficient development of its economy. Achieving this requires the rational use of available resources. In the context of regional planning, the structure of the total resource potential plays an important role in assessing future national economic development and growth [18].

Azerbaijan's strategic location at the crossroads of Europe and Asia, combined with its rich cultural heritage and unique natural resources, makes it well-suited for the development of event tourism [19].

In recent years, the country has successfully hosted a number of major international events. Mega-events are large-scale, multipurpose occasions that reflect culture globalization, international relations, and the growing influence of politics and economics on event programming and organization [20]. Among the most prominent examples are the Formula 1 Grand Prix in Baku, the European Games, the IV Islamic Solidarity Games, and the International Astronautical Congress. These

events have strengthened Azerbaijan's image as an attractive tourist destination and showcased its capacity to organize world-class events [21].

A significant milestone was Azerbaijan's victory in the Eurovision Song Contest in 2011, which gave the country the opportunity to host the event in Baku in 2012. Eurovision served as a powerful catalyst for the development of tourism infrastructure and for enhancing Azerbaijan's international image. The successful organization of such a high-profile event demonstrated the country's potential as a hub for event tourism and laid the groundwork for attracting future large-scale events. It also highlighted mechanisms that could be applied to improve event tourism across different regions of Azerbaijan, thereby contributing to their socio-economic development.

As noted by the Minister of Culture and Tourism of Azerbaijan, *"During the 15 days of the Eurovision Song Contest 2012, more than 100,000 tourists visited Azerbaijan. Over 50,000 people came to Baku specifically to watch Eurovision 2012 and to take part in this musical celebration. The successful hosting of Eurovision 2012 contributed to an even greater flow of tourists to Azerbaijan"* [22].

Another landmark event was Baku's debut as a Formula 1 host city in 2016. This decision offered local and international fans the chance to experience the excitement of races running through the streets of the capital. The inclusion of Baku in the Formula 1 calendar underscored its growing importance in the world of sports and boosted its appeal to both travelers and motorsport enthusiasts. With the exception of 2020, when the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the global calendar, Baku has continued to host the event annually, drawing thousands of spectators. The race has served not only as a competition venue but also as a platform to showcase the culture and heritage of Azerbaijan [23; 24]. The economic impact has been substantial. In 2016-2017, revenues from Formula 1 in Baku amounted to \$277.3 million, including \$164.2 million in profit. Around 1,000 businesses were involved, while tourism, hotel, and transport services generated \$22.7 million. According to the Baku City Circuit operating company, during the first four years the Grand Prix contributed \$500 million to Azerbaijan's economy.

Tourist flows have also increased significantly. For instance, in 2022, 70,000 visitors from 10 countries came to Baku for the Grand Prix. By April 2023, the State Tourism Agency reported 154,233 visitors from more than 100 countries, representing a 1,442% increase compared to April 2022 (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Number of tourists attending the Formula 1 Azerbaijan Grand Prix, [25]

In July 23-29, 2024, the DREAM Fest 2024 International Music Festival took place in Baku. This large-scale open-air event was held at the Sea Breeze Resort complex, located on the shores of the Caspian Sea. The festival brought together 250 renowned musicians, including past Eurovision Song Contest participants, representing the CIS countries, Turkey, the United Kingdom, Europe, and Canada. Over six days, DREAM Fest 2024 presented audiences with an impressive program featuring popular hits from different eras. The event attracted a substantial number of visitors from Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Georgia, the United Kingdom, the United States, and various European countries. According to the organizers, more than 60,000 people attended the festival during the six days [26].

The distinctive architecture and infrastructure of the Sea Breeze Resort, founded by Emin Agalarov in 2006, have contributed to its transformation into a tourist destination offering European-level services. In the future, the main events of the DREAM Fest music festival are planned to be held there. Thus, DREAM Fest 2024 is expected to significantly enhance Azerbaijan's international profile, attracting tourists and strengthening cultural ties with a range of countries. The festival also contributes to the development of the local economy by increasing tourist flows and stimulating the growth of tourism infrastructure. In addition, it promotes Azerbaijan as a modern and culturally rich destination, reinforcing its position on the global tourism map.

Further evidence of international confidence in Azerbaijan is the decision to host the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP29), scheduled for November 11-22, 2024. This decision, adopted at the COP28 plenary session in Dubai in December 2023, highlights Azerbaijan's growing importance in the international arena and its capacity to host large-scale events.

As the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan stated: "COP29 cannot be compared with events held so far. Even recalling the European Games, 5,000 athletes and about 3,000 accompanying guests arrived. But tens of thousands of foreign representatives will come to COP29 in our country, and for two weeks Baku will become the center of the world. According to some estimates, approximately 70,000 to 80,000 foreign guests are expected to visit our country during this period. I believe that COP29 is one of the most prestigious international events in the world. From the point of view of the representation of countries, it is not inferior to the UN General Assembly" [27].

Such large-scale events should be regarded not only as a significant investment in the country's image, but also as a contribution to the future development of Azerbaijan's tourism industry. International experience shows that hosting global events allows developing countries to position themselves as attractive, safe destinations capable of welcoming large numbers of tourists.

Regional events held in Azerbaijan

At the same time, a variety of holidays and festivals are held annually across the regions of Azerbaijan, contributing to the development of event tourism (see Table 1).

Table 1

Festive events and festivals organized across Azerbaijani regions

Festival	Year Established	Location	Period	Significance
Pomegranate Festival	2006	Goychay	October 26 – November 7	Promotes Goychay as the center of pomegranate culture, attracts tourists, stimulates infrastructure development, and supports agriculture.
Gabala International Music Festival	2009	Gabala	Late July – early August	Encourages cultural exchange, strengthens Gabala's image as a cultural hub, and attracts music enthusiasts.
Uzeyir Hajibeyli International Music Festival	2009	Baku	September 18 (Uzeyir Hajibeyli's birthday)	Highlights Azerbaijan's musical heritage and draws attention to the work of one of the country's most prominent composers, fostering interest in classical music.

Apple Festival	2012	Guba	During the apple harvest season	Promotes agricultural products and supports agritourism, attracting tourists interested in gastronomy and farming.
Persimmon Festival	2017	Balakan	During the persimmon harvest season	Supports local agriculture, popularizes persimmons, and attracts gastronomic tourism.
Grape and Wine Festival	2019	Meysari village, Shamakhi District	August 30	Develops wine culture and stimulates economic growth through agritourism.
National Yaylag Festival	2019	Gadabay District	Late July	Promotes Azerbaijan's national and spiritual values, while preserving and popularizing nomadic culture at the international level.
Khari Bulbul Music Festival	2021	Shusha, Jidir Duzu	Summer	Promotes Shusha's status as the cultural capital, stimulates tourism, and draws attention to the region's unique heritage
International Culinary Festival	2022	Shusha	Early May	Showcases the richness of Azerbaijani cuisine, attracts gastronomic tourism, and fosters cultural exchange.
Cherry and Sour Cherry Festival	2022	Khachmaz	June 25	Supports agriculture, promotes regional products, and attracts tourists.
Balloon Festival	2023	Meysari village, Shamakhi District	June 17-18	Promotes the tourism potential of the Shamakhi region and beyond.

Source: [28].

The organization of these and other festivals plays a crucial role in the development of event tourism. They contribute to economic growth, foster cultural exchange, and promote the international visibility of Azerbaijan's regions, with the overarching aim of strengthening their tourism potential.

Challenges in organizing event tourism in Azerbaijan's regions

Despite these achievements, the development of event tourism in Azerbaijan's regions faces several challenges. Numerous areas lack modern infrastructure, qualified personnel, effective marketing strategies, and sufficient financial resources for hosting large-scale events [29]. These limitations restrict their ability to attract both tourists and investors, reducing competitiveness in the international market.

For example, the First National Yaylag Festival (July 26-28, 2019), held at the Duzyurd-Miskinli pasture in the Gadabay region, welcomed over 100 international guests from 16 countries and attracted more than 50,000 visitors. The Second National Yaylag Festival (July 29-31), held in the town of Hajikend (Ganja), hosted around 300

guests from 22 countries. The events were organized with the participation of the Ministries of Culture, Youth and Sports, and Agriculture, as well as the State Tourism and Employment Agencies, local executive authorities of Ganja and the Goygol region, and various private organizations [30].

However, the events also revealed organizational shortcomings. Visitors and media representatives expressed dissatisfaction in both publications and social media posts, citing inadequate transport infrastructure as the main issue. Heavy rainfall caused road washouts and mudslides, blocking bus routes and creating severe traffic congestion. In addition, kiosk prices for food and drinks were inflated three- to fivefold, further frustrating attendees.

The second Yaylag Festival in Ganja, despite stronger institutional support, faced similar problems with transport, weather conditions, inflated prices, and overall organization. Comparable difficulties arose during the Shamakhi Balloon Festival. These examples highlight the urgent need for an integrated approach to event planning that prioritizes reliable infrastructure, fair pricing, and the comfort and safety of participants and guests.

More broadly, in an increasingly competitive global tourism market, destinations must focus on creating unique and attractive products. Regional disparities in readiness and capacity only add to the challenges, underscoring the importance of coordinated, strategic development in Azerbaijan's event tourism sector.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this regard, the following mechanisms are proposed to enhance the implementation of events in the regions of Azerbaijan:

1. Infrastructure development. A key step is to improve transport accessibility, modernize roads, and expand public transport. The lack of adequate transport infrastructure remains the main barrier for tourists and media representatives attending events in the regions of Azerbaijan.
2. Financing and investment. It is essential to attract investors and provide government support in the form of subsidies, grants, and tax incentives for event organizers. For example, in Turkey and in parts of Eastern and Central Europe, travel companies benefit from VAT exemptions, while in South Korea, government grants support major international events.

3. Marketing and promotion. Turkey effectively promotes its cultural and historical events through television advertising, social media, and international tourism exhibitions. In 2016, the Georgian National Tourism Administration produced the video Summer in Georgia, which was broadcast in 16 countries. Active use of social media, websites, blogs, and multilingual advertising materials is crucial for promoting events.
4. Education and training. Regular training sessions and seminars should be held to improve the qualifications of event organizers and tourism professionals. The UK's Association of Professional Event Organisers (MPI), for example, runs such programs. Turkey also implements a well-developed personnel policy in event tourism, which has significantly contributed to the growth of its tourism sector.
5. Technological innovation. Modern information technologies should be used to manage and promote events, including online ticket sales, virtual tours, and mobile applications, practices already adopted worldwide. Partnerships with international organizations can also facilitate experience-sharing and attract large-scale events. For example, with World Bank support, Georgia developed a national long-term tourism strategy.
6. Social responsibility and cultural integration. Event organization should consider the interests of local communities and support their social and economic development. The active involvement of residents in event preparation and delivery fosters cultural integration and creates a distinctive atmosphere. At Munich's Oktoberfest, for instance, residents sell local products, contributing to the festival's popularity.
7. Evaluation and monitoring. Systems of regular analysis and monitoring should be introduced to assess event effectiveness. For example, research conducted at Oktoberfest examines its economic impact on Munich. In 2023, around 6 million people attended the two-week festival, consuming about 7 million liters of beer. At an average price of 13 euros per liter, this generated roughly 91 million euros from beer sales alone. Organizers also monitor the popularity of traditional Bavarian dishes and entertainment among guests.
8. Event calendar diversification. A broad range of events should be organized, including cultural festivals, sports competitions, gastronomic fairs, music concerts, and business conferences. In Germany, Munich hosts a variety of such events—from Oktoberfest and film festivals to Christmas markets and concerts—attracting diverse tourist groups.

9. Public-private partnerships. Cooperation between public institutions and private companies should be encouraged to co-finance and organize events. Public-private partnership (PPP) models—such as concession agreements, leasing, and joint enterprises—are particularly effective for building transport infrastructure and ensuring accessibility to tourist destinations.
10. International cooperation. Partnerships with global organizations and event tourism associations are important for exchanging knowledge and experience.
11. Safety and security. Many countries hosting large-scale events apply advanced technologies and procedures to ensure the safety of participants and visitors, including medical services, video surveillance, and evacuation planning.

Taken together, these mechanisms can create more favorable conditions for event tourism development in Azerbaijan's regions, enhance event quality, and increase their attractiveness to tourists. This will, in turn, stimulate local economic growth and strengthen the country's international image. Integrating innovative approaches with global best practices, while considering local specificities, will ensure the sustainable and successful development of event tourism in Azerbaijan.

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The author have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Reema Singh. Poddar International College, Jaipur (India)